

DESIGN AND CHARACTERIZATION OF PRESSURE, TEMPERATURE AND MOISTURE SENSORS BASED ON MWCNT COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

There were developed MWCNT-composite sensors with epoxy, PVA, rubber and glass matrices for direct measurement of external pressure, temperature and moisture changing with use of TaunitTM as nanotubes material. Electrical conductivity of sensors can be tuned by changing of mass fraction of MWCNT. Amount of MWCNT was varied from 1 to 5% mass for epoxy and glass matrices, and up to 50% mass of dry content for PVA matrix. Sensitivity of glass-MWCNT composite sensors was changed by changing consolidation conditions or by agglomeration state for epoxy, PVA or rubber matrix. PVA-based composite was extremely sensitive to moisture changing but silicon rubber- and glass-based ones were near insensitive to moisture changing. Main feature of MWCNT suspension in basic media is agglomerate's microstructure, because there is impossible to have ideal dispersing of natural CNT agglomerates onto individual carbon nanotubes. State of agglomeration's structure could be characterized by log-normal distribution and it significantly influences electrical and mechanical behavior of sensors.

For good dispersion of MWCNT into basic viscous matrices or glass-powder we used Mazerustar kk50 planetary mixer and small zirconia spheres (1.5...2 mm dia). Consolidation of MWCNT-glass composite was done at the different pressure (up to 500 bar) and different temperature (up to 450 degrees Celsius). MWCNT- polyvinyl alcohol/silicon rubber composites were cured at room conditions with aramid fabric substrate to have regular structure of sensor.

Most sensitive materials for pressure and temperature changing were made with elastomeric matrix like PVA or silicon rubber, because strain of these low stiffness media could be much higher in comparison with strain of epoxides or glass filled by CNTs at the same pressure or temperature.

1 INTRODUCTION

One of the promising directions of obtaining materials with desired properties - modification of carbon nanostructures (nanotubes, graphene, etc.). This allows obtaining materials with significantly better thermal conductivity, mechanical, electrical and other properties. Insulating materials filled carbon nanotubes (CNTs) have high electrical conductivity under low volumetric content (1-3%) [1, 2]. Electric conductivity of materials under indicated low content of electrically conductive particles is defined by tunnel effect [3-5], appearing between individual nanotubes. Modified material becomes sensitive to external factors such as temperature, moisture, pressure or strain, etc. Nanomaterial sensitivity is determined by electrical resistance, mainly depending of the distances between the nanotubes, which change under the external factors influence [6, 7]. Sensors on the basis

of CNT can have wide range of overall dimensions (from several microns to several centimetres), high sensitivity and a wide range of applications due to the possibility of using different matrix materials. As of now, several CNT sensors types were designed [6-12].

CNT-based sensors have better properties under homogeneous state of the material [13-15], which prevents their higher inclination to agglomeration [16, 17]. Following methods are used to solve this problem: sonication treatment [18-20], high shear mixing [18, 21, 22], ball milling [18, 23, 24], centrifugal mixing [25] and others. These methods don't always allow obtaining required material quality and, in most cases, carbon nanotubes dispersion quality verification is hindered.

In this paper, we consider method of preparing nanocomposites, based on different materials containing of carbon nanotubes. Preparation of material was performed using a planetary mixer and ceramic milling balls. Sensitivity coefficients of the material under changing pressure, temperature and moisture were determined.

2 MATERIALS

Taunit-MD was used in this work as MWCNT material. This material is presented by filamentary structures of the polycrystalline graphite in the form of bulk powder from black agglomerates. Agglomerates of micrometric size have structure of crossed bundles of multiwall tubes. Taunit-MD is a modified material with improved morphological and physical-mechanical parameters (Table 1).

Taunit-MD parameters control was performed by a transmission electron microscope JEOL JEM-2100. Images analysis shows than individual CNT size in collapsed form is 2 - 5 times smaller, than spread CNT length.

Parameters		Taunit-MD
Outside diameter	nm	8-15
Inside diameter	nm	4-8
Length	μm	2 and more
Total admixtures volume (after treating)	%	up to 5 (up to 1)
Balk density	g/cm^3	0.03-0.05
Specific geometrical surface	m^2/g	300-320 and more
Thermal stability	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	up to 600

Table 1: CNT Taunit-MD general characteristics [26].

Upon our research data CNT outside diameter is from 10 to 50 nm, inside diameter is from 3 to 8 nm, length is more than 2 μm .

3 NANOCOMPOSITE PREPARATION

Following materials were used as the nanocomposite matrix: epoxy resin, silicon rubber, PVA, and silicate glass.

In order to achieve improved electrical and mechanical features of the nanocomposite material, it is desirable to use separate carbon nanotubes, as they are more pliable and have improved electrical properties, which leads to increasing sensitivity of the composite, with minimal loading of the carbon material. In order to make used product parameters closer to ideal, it is necessary do disperse CNT by high shear mixing in viscous media. Such exposure allows fracturing of large agglomerates and uniform distributing of the tubes in matrix media, producing homogenous suspension.

CNT dispersion was performed in mixer KURABO Mazerustar kk250, under mode 9-8, corresponding to platform rotating speed of 1,700 rpm, and container rotation speed of 1,580 rpm. Dispersing was performed in epoxy resin ED-20 by means of milling balls from zirconium oxide (ZnO_2), with diameter of 1.2 - 1.5 mm and total weight, equal to mixture weight. During rotation milling balls in the vessel generate shear forces, facilitating mechanical failure and separation of associated particles (agglomerates). Particle size analysis showed that average size of the agglomerate after dispersion was equal to 1.16 μm and maximum size - to 15.5 μm (Fig. 1a). The dependence of the agglomerates size of the CNT dispersion time in epoxy is shown in Fig. 2.

A mixture of silicate glass and CNT have been prepared using mixer KURABO Mazerustar kk250 with the same parameters that for epoxy suspension. Glass was previously milled to a particle size less than 30 microns (Fig. 1b). Prepared powder was further sintered at 350 °C and pressure of 500 bar for 30 minutes. As a result, 25 mm dia, cylindrical specimens were obtained, and density was equal to 1,890-1,980 kg/m³.

Preparing suspension based on rubber and PVA was performed in the same way as the epoxy suspension.

Figure 1: Micrograph of CNT material dispersing: epoxy resin suspension (left), silicate glass mix (right).

Figure 2: Dependence of the CNT agglomerates in epoxy size of dispersion time.

There were prepared four types of specimens from the current materials:

1) Test specimens from epoxy resin, placed between two layers of copper, shown on Fig. 3a. Weight fractions of CNT in specimens were equal to 1%, 3%, and 5%. Dimensions of specimens were 25x10x1 mm.

2) Silicate glass-based test specimens were formed as rectangular plates with dimensions of 20x8x1 mm, Fig. 3b. They were cut from the cylinder of sintered bulk material. Silver powder glue was used to make conductor's zones. Weight fractions of CNT in specimens were equal to 1%, 3%, and 5%.

3) Silicon rubber-based test specimens were made in the form of a thin coating (30x15x0.1 mm) over an aramid fabric, Fig. 3c. Silver wires were used to form electrical contacts. Weight fractions of CNT in specimens were equal to 7% and 14%.

4) Test specimens with PVA-based CNT-material were produced using the same technology as for silicon rubber-based specimens. Weight fractions of CNT in specimens were equal to 25% and 50% (based on dry substance PVA).

a) Epoxy-based specimens

b) Silicate glass-based specimens

c) Rubber-based specimens

Figure 3: Specimens of nanocomposite based on epoxy resin, silicate glass and rubber matrix (1 - place for contacts soldering; 2 – copper plates; 3 – test nanocomposite; 4 - current conducting glue; 5 - silver conductors; 6 - copper conductors).

Nanocomposite specimens with the lowest weight content of CNT (1%) have high resistance, more than 20 Mega Ohm, making it difficult to carry out research on these specimens. Therefore, these specimens were excluded from the study.

4 ELECTRICAL CONDUCTIVITY DEPENDENCE OF TEMPERATURE

All tests were carried out using oven Instron 3019-410. Sensor specimens were placed into oven, air temperature was varied from 30 to 90 °C, with increment of 10 °C.

Measurements were performed by double-contacts method, by means of digital measuring device LCR (LCR-78101G), manufactured by Good Will Instrument Co. Ltd. (GW Instek). Sensors resistance was monitored under constant voltage of 2V.

Dependences of specimens resistance of temperature are shown in Fig. 4.

a) Epoxy-based sensor resistance dependency of temperature

b) Glass-based sensor resistance dependency of temperature

c) Silicon rubber-based sensor resistance dependency of temperature

Figure 4: Sensors resistance dependency from temperature changing.

Table 2 presents thermal sensitivity coefficients (changing of electrical resistance with the temperature changing on 1 °C) for tested sensors, with different matrix materials and different weight fractions of CNT.

Thermal sensitivity coefficient, Ohm/°C						
Matrix material	CNT content, %	Specimen number				
		1	2	3	4	5
Epoxy	3	0.96	0.62	0.85	1.15	0.58
	5	0.057	0.012	0.023	0.016	0.013
Silicate glass	3	0.11	0.10	0.12	0.011	0.09
	5	0.07	0.05	0.05	0.07	0.03
Silicone rubber	7	0.093	0.040	0.08	-	-
	14	0.020	0.011	0.024	-	-

Table 2: Thermal sensitivity coefficients.

Specimens resistance changing under temperature increasing is explained by two mechanisms, the first - increasing the distance between the nanotubes due the thermal expansion of the matrix material, and the second - resistance change of individual CNTs. According to the paper [27], individual nanotubes resistance when heating from 30 to 90°C can reduce more than 10%. Since the CNTs are not fully contact with each other at lower concentration, it is reasonable that the effect of individual CNT temperature dependence has less impact on overall nanocomposite temperature dependence. Likely, decreasing in the test specimens resistance is associated with disproportionate changing in the dimensions of the specimens matrix due to the substrates used (as copper, glass and aramid fabric).

As we can see from the table, specimens with lower CNT content are characterized with higher thermal sensitivity coefficient.

5 ELECTRICAL CONDUCTIVITY DEPENDENCE OF PRESSURE

Pressure tests were performed on machine Instron 5942. In order to apply pressure with uniform distribution, specimen was compressed between steel plates through soft rubber ply. Pressure was increased from zero to 30 bar.

Conductivity measurements were also performed by double-contacts method, by means of digital device LCR-78101G under constant voltage of 2 V.

Results of resistance changing under pressure are shown in Table 3.

Electrical resistance, Ohm											
Matrix material	CNT content, %	Specimen number									
		1		2		3		4		5	
		Pressure, bar									
		0	30	0	30	0	30	0	30	0	30
Epoxy	3	184.75	184.58	262.95	262.80	444.55	443.64	452.00	451.67	527.40	526.62
	5	92.580	92.307	24.860	23.730	53.708	53.104	37.472	37.245	50.670	50.631
Silicate glass	3	159.99	159.42	180.71	179.57	166.02	164.79	185.02	184.82	156.53	156.33
	5	104.65	104.54	71.397	71.312	92.556	92.371	101.57	101.53	123.32	129.37
Rubber	7	122.74	112.24	45.103	38.803	92.440	63.040	-	-	-	-
	14	16.167	15.687	14.108	13.970	28.622	28.484	-	-	-	-

Table 3: Results of measuring resistance of the specimens under pressure

Table 4 presents pressure sensitivity coefficients (changing of electrical resistance with the pressure changing on 1 bar) for tested sensors, with different matrix materials and weight fraction of CNTs.

Resistance decreased with increasing of pressure, because distance between CNTs decreased and contact surface between CNTs increased.

Pressure sensitivity coefficient, Ohm/bar						
Matrix material	CNT content, %	Specimen number				
		1	2	3	4	5
Epoxy	3	0.057	0.05	0.08	0.067	0.033
	5	0.0091	0.037	0.020	0.0076	0.0013
Silicate glass	3	0.019	0.038	0.041	0.0068	0.0068
	5	0.0037	0.0028	0.0062	0.0013	0.21
Silicon rubber	7	0.35	0.21	0.98	-	-
	14	0.016	0.0067	0.0046	-	-

Table 4: Pressure sensitivity coefficients.

Rubber-based sensors with lower CNT content have higher sensitivity, because they have lower stiffness due to ease of compression.

6 MOISTURE SENSITIVITY

Sensors were placed in a container with distilled water for 10 minutes. Electrical resistance changed and was measured by LCR-78101G. Sensitivity to changes of moisture was determined for specimens based on PVA-matrix, Table 5. Sensors based on glass, epoxy resin and rubber exhibited poor sensitivity to water, because they had no porosity and PVA nanocomposite had significant open porosity.

CNT content, %	Specimen number	Electrical resistance, Ohm		Resistance change
		Initial state	Final state	
25	1	231	815	3.53
	2	216	728	3.38
	3	207	754	3.65
50	1	57.1	95.4	1.67
	2	48.1	94.3	1.96
	3	75.3	121	1.61

Table 5: Change in resistance of PVA-based nanocomposite when immersed in water.

As seen from the table, the sensitivity of the specimens with a lower content CNT is twice higher.

7 CONCLUSIONS

We have fabricated functional composite nanomaterial containing CNT. Following results were obtained:

1) We've developed technological process of fabricating functional nanocomposite on the basis of epoxy resin/silicate glass/silicon rubber/PVA and CNTs of Taunit-MD type. A method of dispersing CNTs in a viscous medium by using a planetary mixer with milling balls was proven.

2) Sensor's electrical resistance can be controlled in the range from several Ohms to thousands Ohms. Sensors with lower CNT content are characterized with higher sensibility, but they were unstable and demonstrated large spread of properties, as CNT content close to the percolation threshold.

3) The most stable sensor matrix material was silicate glass, but due to high stiffness the material sensitivity to pressure and temperature is lower than for epoxy-based or silicon rubber-based sensors.

This work shows great potential for different application of sensors with MWCNT-composite, for example in 'smart house' projects to signal about water leakage, overheating of water/air or overpressure of tubes.

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